

PEDAGOGICAL- PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF DEVELOPING STUDENTS` FOREIGN LANGUAGE LEARNING ABILITIES

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Abstract: Identifying alternative and variable methods for learning, understanding, perceiving, and retaining foreign languages is a key factor in improving the effectiveness of education. According to psychological approaches, language learning abilities enhance a person's speech skills and require consistent practice. Learning foreign languages significantly impacts students' personal, intellectual, and cultural development, and psychology plays an essential role in this process. This article explores the pedagogical and psychological aspects of developing students' foreign language learning abilities.

Keywords: ability, education, process, linguistics, logic, motivation, skill, potential.

In all stages of the education system, providing quality education and preparing competitive professionals in the era of globalization has become a pressing issue. The need to develop mechanisms for shaping modern skills among learners and renewing existing methodologies based on international approaches is growing. One of the critical tasks for researchers, particularly educators, is to create approaches and methods aimed at acquiring and using foreign languages, recognized as a modern skill.

Identifying alternative and variable methods for learning, understanding, perceiving, and retaining foreign languages is vital in enhancing educational effectiveness. Today, implementing advanced global methods and experiences in the national education system has shown positive results in acquiring modern skills and knowledge. Regardless of the method or approach used by educators to teach modern skills, it is necessary that it contributes to the quality and outcomes of the education.

Learning a foreign language has become a significant issue in the modern world. It serves as a tool for intercultural communication, gaining importance on the international stage and being required at all levels of education, from schools to universities. However, the acquisition of foreign languages involves not only linguistic but also psychological aspects. Motivation, abilities, and interest in the language play a crucial role in language acquisition. In this context, the interest in learning a language and the opportunity to use it practically serve as powerful motivational factors. As the global economy develops, knowledge of foreign languages often leads to financial and professional success.

According to psychological approaches, language learning abilities enhance an individual's speech skills and require continuous practice. At the same time, communicative education is one of the essential methods in language learning. This approach focuses on acquiring a foreign language as a communication tool, prioritizing not grammatical knowledge but the content and significance of communication. This method helps develop the student's ability to communicate in social situations.

In addition to language learning abilities, discursive and strategic abilities are also crucial in the communicative education process. Through these abilities, students organize effective communication in foreign languages in practical situations. Therefore, the teaching methods used in the process of learning modern English must focus not only on linguistic aspects but also on the development of personal motivation and abilities.

It is important to note that any ability allows the development of specific knowledge and skills. Therefore, a person with inherent abilities, if they do not know or choose not to learn or work, may achieve less in life. In contrast, those who are hardworking and capable of learning, despite having less innate potential, often achieve more success in the long run.

Like all languages, foreign language abilities can be developed at any age. While children and adolescents tend to acquire languages faster and more easily, adults possess distinct advantages in language learning, such as developed logic and self-organization skills. These traits do not constitute language ability themselves, but they create a favorable environment for the growth of language potential.

To develop students' language learning abilities, linguistics can be supplemented with simple, seemingly unrelated elements. Language learning abilities can be divided into cognitive-linguistic and communicative-speech categories. Communication and speech refer to the abilities that ensure effective interaction with others and psychological adaptability in joint tasks. Cognitive-linguistic abilities refer to the skills and techniques that help in the rapid acquisition of language systems, such as vocabulary, phonetics, and grammar. The traditional education system focuses on the development of cognitive-linguistic abilities, while intensive teaching systems help develop communicative-speech abilities.

Recently, there has been an increasing interest in focusing on the individual's creative potential as the object of learning and education. Therefore, the goal of education is not only to accumulate knowledge and skills but also to teach students methods of work, develop their cognitive qualities, personal virtues, and intellectual and speech activity.

Typically, in the initial stages of foreign language learning, students have high motivation, but in general, there are students with low motivation, especially in foreign language classes. To accelerate and assist the development of students' language learning abilities, teaching methods must be shaped. The learning material for such students should be simplified as much as possible. This process can be long and sometimes take several months. However, with the first successes, students realize that they are not "inferior to others" and, as a result, develop further interest and motivation to learn the language.

In this process, students will begin to make voluntary efforts to master the material, as they see a real opportunity to learn the language, increasing their self-esteem and satisfaction with themselves and their academic activities. Only when positive learning motivation emerges can language learning abilities begin to develop, and the success achieved due to increased abilities will, in turn, strengthen further motivation.

Targeted development of students' abilities does not eliminate differences among them: in a developing educational environment, some students may progress faster than others. However, because the teacher contributes to the development of all students, these differences become most apparent in the advanced stages of individual ability development.

There is a system of didactic tools aimed at developing the cognitive-linguistic and communicative-speech aspects of foreign languages. This system works effectively in conditions where elements and methods of intensive teaching are actively applied, as it takes into account psychophysiological conditions and students' individual characteristics, stimulates both conscious and unconscious cognitive processes, strengthens the language base, encourages communication, and creates favorable conditions for effective teacher-student interaction.

This, first and foremost, involves the organization of the educational process. The didactic tools system assumes the complex, interconnected operation of all components of language ability, but it is important to describe the development process of each component separately to facilitate perception.

Without this, it is impossible to understand the foundations of behavior, thinking, consciousness, and the unconscious. The pedagogical-psychological aspects of developing students' language learning abilities require in-depth knowledge of memory. Foreign language teachers consider good memory a crucial factor in both the initial and later stages of foreign language acquisition. Both mechanical and logical types of memory are of particular interest. It is well-known that these types of memory differ in the methods of memorization.

Mechanical memorization is simple and often carried out through repetition, which can also occur without conscious thought or understanding. In the initial stages of language teaching, techniques and methods for developing visual, imagery, and auditory memory are generally used. They all rely on the principle of clarity, which serves a motivating function.

It is essential to emphasize that the pedagogical-psychological aspects of developing students' language learning abilities not only define the goals, tasks, and motivation of teaching but also determine the unique methods and approaches to learning. Therefore, the significance of foreign language teaching should not be overlooked. Language learning plays a vital role in the personal, intellectual, and cultural development of students, and psychology plays a significant role in this process.

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